

Research

Mauritanian Effect of Trade Openness on Economic Growth

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Abstract : *The main Objective of this paper is to analyze the effect of trade openness on Mauritanian economic growth. Thus trade openness is considered as a central and explanatory element towards convergence between countries. It turns out that international trade is one of the essential levers of the Mauritanian economy; the objective of this study was to analyze the effect of trade openness on the economic growth of Mauritania over a period from 1986 to 2016. The empirical and theoretical literature exists on this problematic but gives contradictory results. To analyze the effect of trade liberalization on growth In Mauritania, we have used the least squares (OLS) method and Vector Autoregressive (VAR) we found our data on World Bank and the Mauritanian national statistical office. The result shows that there is a positive relationship between trade openness and Mauritanian economic growth.*

Keywords: *Trade openness, economic growth, ordinary least square (OLS), Vector Autoregressive (VAR)*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

many African countries have decided to liberalize their activities during the last two decades, trade has played a very important role in the economies of these countries at different levels of development, trade has not only contributed to a more efficient allocation of resources within countries, but also by sharing the growth from part of the

world to the other. In recent decades, the world's economies have become increasingly linked, thanks to increased trade.

International trade has often played a central role in the history of developing countries. A particular economic result for a country often committed by governments for their international trade in order to produce the economic impact that trade has always had on civilizations, however, there are different static and dynamic gains in trade between countries, but nothing in trade theory says that revenues are distributed equally.

It was in 1947 that trade liberalization began after the Second World War with the entry into force of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT).

The GATT was negotiated in 1947 by 23 countries; including 12 industrialized countries and 11 developing countries. One of the main objectives of GATT creation was to reduce trade barriers. The GATT was then replaced by the WTO (World Trade Organization) in 1994. The main objective of trade liberalization is to facilitate trade between countries and to enable countries that actually produce for the export of their goods and services to others and imports of goods and services they produce are ineffective. This statement refers to the theory of comparative advantages. Traditional business explanations as "drivers of growth" and their impact on economic development are rooted in the principles of comparative advantage. The theory of comparative advantage comes mainly from the nineteenth century free trade model, associated with David Ricardo and John Stuart Mill, which were later modified by trade theories embedded in the Heckscher-Ohlin theory of proportionality of factors (1933), Stolper-Samuelson (1941). Mauritania's trade regime has been liberalized since the late 1980s, and Mauritania has embarked on economic reforms aimed at liberalizing its economy and foreign trade, and strengthening the legislative framework. The main reforms have focused on: price liberalization and removal of barriers to international trade; exchange liberalization, consolidation of the financial sector; progressive privatization of state-owned enterprises; and tax, customs and judicial reforms.

Structural reforms laid the groundwork for sustained economic development and significantly improved the business climate in the country. Thanks to the reforms initiated in the early 1990s, Mauritania's economic performance between 1996 and 2000 was solid, with an average real GDP growth rate of over 4%, while the annual inflation rate of the CPI has remained below 5%.

The reform of public enterprises and the privatization program put in place have increased considerably, from an average of 15% in the mid-1990s to more than 22% of GDP in 2000. The

current account deficit (excluding official transfers) has been reduced to an average of about 11% of GDP in 1996-2000, and official reserves increased to the equivalent of 7 months of imports at the end of 2000. Export growth, however, lagged and was even negative in 1997-99. Between 1995 and 1999, even taking into account positive economic growth in 1995 and 1996, Mauritania's exports fell by 3% per year, while world exports increased by 2% per year. In the late 1990s, the trade regime was greatly simplified and made more liberal. Tariff rates have been lowered, the number of applicable tariffs has been reduced, the reference prices have been officially abolished, the tariff classification has been replaced by the harmonized system and import licenses, monopolies and the quotas have been removed. World markets have been unfavorable to Mauritania's main export products in recent years. In fact, iron ores and frozen octopus recorded negative global growth in the second half of the 1990s. In addition, Mauritanian exports have been poor in these two markets, as evidenced by the loss of productivity. Mauritania's exports are concentrated on fishery products and mining products (iron ore), with a clear evolution in recent years in favor of mining products and characterized by the predominance of some products. While official statistics do not take into account exports of raw agricultural products other than fish. Attempts to diversify the export base have so far been limited, partly because of low foreign direct investment. Investment that could have assisted in the production, distribution and packaging of fresh produce and agricultural and livestock products. Thus, the role of trade and trade policy reforms in Mauritania remains not only debatable, but it also raises serious questions about the development strategy. Many researchers agree that trade liberalization has not worked because of the combination of internal and external problems. However, other researchers argue that trade liberalization has achieved the most significant results in history. As a result, it was necessary for this study to assess the effect of trade liberalization on Mauritanian economic growth.

1.2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Manni and Afzal in 2012 said that the economies of the countries which have the possibility of stimulating growth and of favoring the global development by the policies of trade liberalization are offered by the economies of the countries which apply the trade liberalization policies.

In addition, as noted in Thirlwall (2000), widespread liberalization of trade in the form of unilateral tariff reductions or the reduction of non-tariff barriers to trade improves growth outcomes. As we know Mauritania has made an important transition to economic liberalization

and strengthening of the legislative framework especially since the early 1980s, and despite this liberalization, Mauritania has achieved solid economic results, and often the economic evolution is irregular. These fluctuations were due to the combined effects of various factors such as severe drought and lower international iron prices, followed by improved weather conditions, iron production and growth in the iron and steel industry. Fishing, favorable climatic conditions and the important development of the fishing sector revitalized the economy, but the economy again experienced a decline in the early 1990s, mainly due to the conflict with Senegal. Only since 1993 has growth resumed at an average annual rate of about 4.5 per cent, reaching a rate of 5 per cent in 2000.

The main factors behind this growth seem to be public investment, often financed by external funds, and exports.

The real GDP growth rate in 2001 was down to 4.6 percent, due to the slowdown in the world economy, particularly the decline in global demand for iron.

As a result, it was necessary for this study to examine the effect of trade liberalization on Mauritania's economic growth. This study thus promised to fill the lack of literature on international trade studies in Mauritania. The overall objective of this study is to examine the effect of trade liberalization on economic growth in Mauritania.

2. THEORITICAL REVIEW

The first economist to study the relationship between international trade and economic growth using the concept of absolute advantage was Adam Smith, from that day on there have been enormous number of economic researches conducted and that raised a very powerful ideas so as to see the impact of free trade policies on the economy of both developed and developing countries. According to Adam Smith (1776), specialization and labor division are considered as the main determinants of wellbeing and economic growth. Besides, the theory of comparative advantage of David Ricardo has showed that both countries engaged in trade can be mutually beneficial from trade and specialization in which his model termed as a “win-win Approach”. It is believed that trade enhances production and consumption efficiency and thus welfare will surge in both countries participating in trade.

In contrast to the above conclusions, no positive relationship is found between trade openness and economic growth of countries. It instead showed that technological progress exogenously determines the factors that affect the long-run economic growth.

Therefore the long run economic growth is not affected by the degree of economic integration with the rest of the world.

Trade openness only has a transitional effect to the steady state and long run welfare gains not on the economy of countries.

According to Lill Anderson & Babula (2009) [...] "conventional trade theory associates international trade with a reallocation of resources within the national borders determined by exogenous differences across countries.

This reallocation of resources generates efficiency gains that increase the level of aggregate national income". Similarly endogenous growth theories suggest that the higher the trade is opened to international competition, the greater the economic growth will be in the sense that it will increase the scale of a spill-overs effect of technology from industrialized economy. Moreover, trade liberalization may encourage growth and development of ones economy for some countries that have a capacity to adopt and imitate the knowledge transferred through the globalization channels such as market and foreign direct investment. But it does not mean that trade liberalization is the only driving factor and also it affects growth positively. In some circumstances, it can be also affect the economy of others inversely Romer & Frankel (1999). David Ricardo's, in the 19 century ,the theory of comparative advantage showed that the more open a country was, the more it allowed it to redirect its scarce resources to more efficient sectors and improve its welfare. Theories that followed confirmed these gains, in addition to adding those related to the remuneration of the factors of production. However, even in the new theories of international trade that take into account returns to scale and imperfect competition, the gains remain static. It is in the theory of growth that one can then come for dynamic gains.

Neo-classical growth models, derived from Solow's (1957) model, assume that technological change is exogenous. In such a framework, a country's trade policies cannot be considered as a factor affecting its growth.

Since the early 1990s, new growth theories have seen technological change as endogenous. It then becomes possible to combine the new theory of international trade with that of endogenous growth. Prebisch (1950) and Singer (1950), however, are concerned with the effects of trade openness on economic growth. By focusing on the nascent industry's argument and lowering the prices of raw materials and primary products, they support inward-looking industrialization strategies for developing countries. Solow's (1956) analysis has shown that a country's trade

policies do not affect economic growth because it is due to exogenous factors. Other works, such as those by Grossman and Helpman (1991), Romer (1990) and Rivera-Batiz and Romer (1991), focus on the long-term implications of government intervention in trade. They see innovation as a source of growth and therefore encourage openness policies. In their models, the gains of free trade come mainly from scale effects conveyed through research and development. The innovation generated contributes to increasing the stock of knowledge and the transfer of technology. In addition, international trade prevents redundant R & D countries from diverting resources from more productive activities. Rodriguez and Rodrik (1999) attest that the net effects of trade opening are uncertain, whether or not they are long-standing. Analyzes and discussion in theory have been made by many economists for the long-term relationship between economic growth and trade liberalization.

Some of them discussed the impact of trade liberalization on economic growth, focusing on its role in promoting technology transfer, foreign capital inflows and positive spillover effects

Kaldor (1970) analyzed the relationship between trade openness and economic growth, where he found that foreign trade demand and economic growth are important determinants of a country's output. Other names, such as Krueger (1978), emphasize the benefits of factors such as returns to scale, indivisibilities and competition. Dollar (1992) argues that turning to the outside world can provide us with capital outside development without serious problems in servicing the corresponding debt. Baroche (1999) whose thesis was confirmed econometrically by O'Rourke (2000), protectionism was favorable to European and American growth in the 19th century. The existence of an economy of scale can justify a positive effect of protection, which also corresponds to the thesis of the incipient industry embodied by F.List (1857). Since the early 1990s, new growth theories have seen technological change as endogenous. It then becomes possible to combine the new theory of international trade with that of endogenous growth. Young (1990) has shown that trade openness for developing countries seems to be more disadvantageous than beneficial for economic growth, but developed countries seem to be more beneficial. Other authors such as Krugman (1987), Lucas (1988), Acemoglu and Zilibotti (2001), Banerjee and Newman (2004) show that openness is not always conducive to growth. Development towards a specialization in low productivity sectors with a total negative impact on growth.

3. MAURITANIAN INTERNATIONAL TRADE

Mauritania is a country open to trade. Most recently, the country signed a free trade agreement with ECOWAS. Foreign trade accounts for more than 100% of the country's GDP.

After a fall in exports of irons and other minerals in 2010, the country's trade balance remained strongly negative due to the increase in the level of imports. Mining exports also suffered from the temporary closure of the Mauritanian National Industrial and Mining Company (SNIM) and the decline in Chinese demand. In 2018, the trade deficit will be reduced by an increase in export earnings of gold and fishery products and a stabilization of imports (lower imports of capital goods into the mining industry). At the end of 2016, Mauritania's trade with the rest of the world amounted to 1,326.1 billion ouguiya, a decrease of 34% compared to 2015. Exports of ore from iron and fishery products (the main products exported) accounted for 29.0% and 41.8% respectively of total export earnings in 2016. Total imports valued at 747.3 billion ouguiya, decreased by 37% over the previous year. The trade balance, structurally deficit, posted a new deficit of 168 billion ouguiya during the year 2016. The rate of coverage of imports by exports was 77.5%, registering an improvement of 9 percentage points. Percentage compared to the previous year. In the fourth quarter of 2017, exports fell by 7.1% in value over the previous quarter (but increased by 6.4% over the previous year) and imports increased by 40.5%. Iron and copper ore, fishery products and gold are Mauritania's main export items.

The country imports mainly petroleum products, wheat, boats, vehicles and machinery.

Trade with the American continent was heavily in deficit due to the sharp rise in imports from the United States (MRO 100 billion). Japan and China remain the two main Asian trading partners of Mauritania in 2016. Despite bilateral deficits with Indonesia (- 6 billion MRO), Malaysia (- 5.4 billion MRO), Thailand (- 5, 4 billion MRO) and India (- 4.5 billion MRO), the overall trade balance with the Asian continent is 140 billion Ouguiya surplus in 2016.

Over the whole of 2016, trade with the Middle East remains a deficit of 87 billion ouguiya, driven mainly by the sharp rise in imports from the United Arab Emirates. With regard to Africa, trade with Mauritania remains weak. In 2016, trade surpluses were recorded with Nigeria (MRO 23 billion), Côte d'Ivoire (MRO 15 billion), and Ghana (MRO 3 Billion), Mali (MRO 2 billion) and Cameroon (2.7 billion MRO). On the other hand, Mauritania's trade with Morocco, Senegal, South Africa, Tunis and Egypt, resulted in the highest trade deficits of the African continent (-57 billion ouguiya).

Table.1.Evolution of Mauritania's foreign trade in value

	2013	2014	2015	2016
Units: million ouguiya				
total external trade	1 380 715	1 659 563	2 005 260	1 326 144
Variation in %	-	20,20%	20,83%	-33,87%

Exportation	<i>807 280</i>	<i>693 966</i>	<i>536 365</i>	<i>578 864</i>
Variations in%	25,09%	12,56%	3,79%	7,92%
Iron-ore	382 412	258 001	130 450	167 654
Gold	106 318	97 303	86 744	78 017
Copper	91 448	65 400	87 478	68 298
Oil	65 334	47 693	23 358	20 423
Fishery products	139 686	203 861	205 960	241 922
Other Product	22 082	21 709	2 376	2 550
Importations	1 197 980	1 099 897	1 181 389	747 280
Variations in%	-	27,85%	35,86%	-37%
Oil products	241 331	226 767	165 655	146 125
Food	125 282	124 722	142 714	128 019
Capital Good	579 116	476 866	671 301	280 872
Construction materials	70 723	75 808	74 731	57 935
Cars and spare parts	70 687	62 586	34 918	38 548
Cigarettes and Tobacco	6 829	7 866	8 149	8 030
Fabrics and clothing	13 192	16 665	14 247	21 354
Cosmetics and Chemicals	29 451	24 510	20 126	19 059
Others products	61 369	84 106	49 548	47 338
Commercial sale	1 371	-103 945	-390 700	-168 416
Coverage Rate	100%	88%	67%	77,5%

Source: Table developed by the author

3.1 EVOLUTION OF MAURITANIAN EXPORT IN 2016

in 2016, exports in value of Mauritania amounted to 579 billion ouguiya, a decrease of 37% compared to 2015. These exports were mainly intended for the countries of the European Union and Asia, and more particularly to China, which accounts for 36% of all exports in value terms in 2016.

Graph.1.Evolution of Mauritania's exports

Source: Table developed by the author

3.1.1 EXPORT OF FISHERY PRODUCT

Overall exports of fishery products amounted to UM 242 billion in 2016, registering a 17% increase over the previous year. In volume terms, following the 14% drop recorded in 2014, these exports were valued at 715,963 tons in 2016, up 13% compared to 2015. By type of species, exports of fishery products in 2016, consist mainly of fresh, chilled or frozen fish which constitutes 83% of the total export earnings of fishery products.

3.1.2. IRON ORE EXPORT

At the end of 2016, exports of iron ore amounted to 12.7 million tons, an increase of 11.9% compared to 2015. In value, these exports amounted to 168 billion ouguiya, increased by 28.5% over the previous year. Depending on the destination, China bought 78% of the quantity of iron exports in 2016, which also represents 75% of the total value.

3.1.3 OTHER EXPORT

In addition to fishery products and iron ore, Mauritania exports gold, copper and petroleum. Indeed, at the end of 2016, exports of gold in value, mainly intended for Switzerland, are valued at 78 billion ouguiya and thus registering a decrease of 10% compared to its level there is a year. The value of exports of copper ore, destined exclusively for China in the amount of 68.3 billion ouguiya, was 22% lower than its value in 2015. Exports of crude oil during the year 2016, recorded a decline of 13% for a value of more than 20.4 billion ouguiya

Graph.2 Mauritania Product Export in 2016

Source: Table developed by the author

3.2 MAURITANIAN IMPORT IN 2016

In value terms, imports amounted to 747.3 billion ouguiya in 2016, down 37% from the previous year, following a sharp drop in imports of capital goods (-58%) and building materials (-22%).

By product type, Mauritania's imports in 2016 mainly consist of capital goods (38%), petroleum products (20%), food products (17%), building materials (8%), mainly from Europe (41%), Asia (17%) and America (15%), while the United States of America (13%), the United Arab Emirates (12%) and China and Belgium with (9%) remain the main suppliers in 2016. United States exports to Mauritania increased from UM 225 billion to UM 100 billion between 2015 and 2016. These imports are capital goods (84%). Those of the United Arab Emirates,

With a (34%) decrease compared to 2015, amounted to 88.8 billion ouguiya, contributing to a bilateral trade deficit of 86 billion ouguiya. Imports of capital goods with 38% of the total value of imports in 2016 amounted to 280.9 billion ouguiya, a decrease of 58% over the previous year. They consist mainly of nuclear reactor properties, boilers, machinery, apparatus and mechanical appliances; parts of these machines or apparatus (38%) and maritime or river transport goods (36%). Imports of capital goods come largely from the United States (30%), Belgium (15%) and Vanuatu (13%). Imports of petroleum products, representing 20% of the value of global imports of the year, amount to 146.13 billion ouguiya, and a reduction of 12% compared to 2015. According to the origin these imports come mainly from the United Arab Emirates (55%) and the Netherlands (27%).

Food imports, valued at 128.19 billion ouguiya in 2016, were down 10 percent from the previous year. Food imports are mainly composed of cereal products (31%), milk and milk products

(17%), animal or vegetable fats and oils (12%) and sugars and sweets (10%). France (14%) remains Mauritania's largest supplier of food products in 2016. Imports of cereals products consist mainly of wheat (73.96%) and rice (25.99%). These cereals come mainly from France (31%), Russia (18%) and Thailand (13%). Imports of building materials, representing less than 8%, decreased by 22% to UM 57.94 billion in 2016. They are composed of iron, iron and steel (33.2%), cement (27.1%) and cast iron, iron and steel (26.8%). These materials are largely imported from China (25%), Turkey (16%), and Morocco (15%).

Graph.3. Mauritania Product Import in 2016

Source: Table developed by the author

Graph.4. Mauritania Import food

Source: Table developed by the author

Table.2.Trade in value of Mauritania with its main partners, in 2016, Unit: Million Ouguiya

COUNTRY	Importations	Exportations	Sales
Global	747 280,11	578 864,16	-168 415,95
Africa	68 586,70	57 887,71	-10 698,99
Nigeria	94,49	23 141,58	23 047,09
Côte d'Ivoire	3 177,55	18 657,21	15 479,66
Ghana	392,61	3 503,14	3 110,53
Mali	1 082,43	3 296,04	2 213,61
Cameroun	1,56	2 720,95	2 719,39
South Africa	2 785,70	1 221,21	-1 564,48
Senegal	5 515,29	928,96	-4 586,33
Tunisia	3 041,23	831,57	-2 209,66
Benin	55,13	687,78	632,65
Democratic Republic of Congo	0,22	563,15	562,92
Togo	0,67	517,13	516,46
Egypt	1 834,38	507,10	-1 327,29
Congo Brazzaville	0,00	400,02	400,02
Liberia	16,48	287,60	271,11
Gabon	390,07	198,97	-191,10
Other	50 198,88	425,31	-49 773,57
Asia	126 307,03	266 904,24	140 597,21
China	67 139,90	206 441,81	139 301,90
Japan	22 008,37	42 146,51	20 138,14
South Korea	386,55	9 024,95	8 638,40
Vietnam	1 508,94	6 003,33	4 494,40
India	5 656,89	1 119,09	-4 537,80
Taiwan	44,74	1 061,69	1 016,95
Thailand	6 112,86	752,79	-5 360,07
Indonesia	6 335,84	184,71	-6 151,13

North Korea	223,80	88,24	-135,56
Malaysia	5 450,56	79,47	-5 371,09
Kazakhstan	0,10	1,66	1,56
Other	11 438,48	0,00	-11 438,48
Middle East	91 321,43	4 177,02	-87 144,41
United Arab Emirates	88 820,40	2 968,88	-85 851,52
Saudi Arabia	1 972,70	967,36	-1 005,34
Lebanon	102,14	236,38	134,24
Other	426,19	4,41	-421,78

Source: Table developed by the author

4. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study is to analyze the effect of trade liberalization on Mauritanian economic growth.

Annual time series data was used from the period of 1986 to 2016. Ordinary least squares OLS has been used to estimate the equation regression. To achieve this, we will use data from the World Bank and the Mauritanian National Statistical Office. Trade liberalization is seen as a source of convergence and a key element for the elaboration of development strategies. Moreover, a good number of international organizations encourage countries to liberalize their trade for some of them, such as the IMF and the World Bank; the liberalization of trade policies is often a major requirement for financial assistance or economic assistance to developing countries.

4.1. ECONOMETRIC MODEL

The objective of this work is to determine the effect of trade liberalization on the economic growth of Mauritania.

These effects will be studied using an econometric model. It is a question of estimating a multiple linear regression equation. GDP is the dependent variable and the explanatory variables are trade openness (TOP), Official development assistant (ODA) and gross domestic capital formation (K).

Gross domestic product or GDP is defined as the sum of the added values realized within a country by all industries for a given period, regardless of the nationality of the enterprises located there. Openness (TOP) is an indicator of the extent of a country's foreign trade. It indicates the country's dependence on the outside world. It is the sum of exports and imports of goods and services measured as a ratio of gross domestic product. It is used as a measure of liberalization. (ODA) Official development assistant, is defined as inter-governmental assistance aimed at promoting the economic development and well-being of developing countries. Loans and credits for military purposes are excluded. Aid can be given bilaterally, from one donor to another, or channeled through a multilateral development agency such as the United Nations or the World Bank. Gross domestic capital formation includes factories, machinery and equipment and is used as an indirect indicator of capital stock.

4.2 MODEL SPECIFICATION

This paper, we use the aggregate production function model for estimation. The production function is given as

$$Y = f(A, K, L) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where Y is real GDP, A is the total factor productivity (TFP) while K and L are the usual capital and labor inputs respectively

Therefore, it is assumed that

$$A = g(\text{OPENNESS}, L, k, \text{oda},) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

By substituting equation (3) for equation (2), we obtain:

$$\text{GDP} = h(\text{TOP}, \text{ODA}, K, \text{and } L) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

However, data on the active employed labor force are not readily available (Ramirez, 2006) so labor (L) is dropped from the model.

Then, equation (3) becomes

$$\text{GDP} = f(\text{OPENNESS}, \text{ODA}, K,) \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

From equation (4), the specific model for the real GDP for the economy is given as:

$$\text{GDP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{TOP} + \beta_2 \text{ODA} + \beta_3 K + \mu t \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Where:

GDP: real Gross Domestic Product

TOP: Trade openness

ODA: Official development assistant

K : gross domestic capital formation

β_i : represent the elasticity coefficients

4.3 DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULT

a. Serial correlation test

Before starting, we first formulate our hypotheses:

H0 (null hypothesis), implies that there is not serial correlation

H1 (alternative hypothesis), implies that there is serial correlation

The prob. F (2,25) is 0.4401 is greater than the critical value (0.05), we fail to one rejects the null hypothesis conclude that there is no serial correlation in the residual.

Table.3. Serial Correlation Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:			
F-Statistic	0.848347	Prob. F(2,25)	0.4401
Obs*R-squared	1.970189	Square(2)	0.3734

Source: Table developed by the author after data analysis

b. Unit Root Test

We did the Unit root test to find out if the variables are stationary or not.

Before we begin we will first give our hypotheses:

H0 (null hypothesis), implies that there is not stationary

H1 (alternative hypothesis), implies that there stationary

When the P value is less than 5% we reject the null hypothesis H0 and When the P value is more than 5% we reject the alternative hypothesis and keep the null hypothesis.

After doing the root unit test, the results obtained are organized in the table (3).

The variables tested are the LGDP Logarithm gross domestic product, trade openness (LTOP). Official development assistant(LODA) and the : gross domestic capital formation(LK).The result shows all the P values of the four variables are greater than 5% which implies that all the

variables has unit root at level its mean that the variable are not stationary at level , but at first difference, all the variable are stationary.

Table.4.Stationary test (ADF)

Variable	LEVE L			FIRST DEFFERENCE		
	ADF	Critica l value At 5%	Result	ADF	Critica l value At 5%	Result
LGDP	-0.051733 0.9460	-2.963972	(0)	-3.947088 0.0052	-2.967767	I(1)
LTOP	-2.388844 0.1532	-2.963972	(0)	-4.451344 0.0015	-2.967767	I(1)
LK	-0.523331 0.8730	-2.963972	(0)	-4.588124 0.0010	-2.967767	I(1)
LODA	-2.556046 0.1133	-2.963972	I0)	-5.244407 0.0002	-2.971853	I(1)

Source: Table developed by the author after data analysis

c. Heteroskedasticity Test

Before we start the analysis, we should formulate our hypothesis:

H0 (Null hypothesis): the residual are homoskedasticity

H1 (Alternative hypothesis): the residual are heteroskedasticity

We know that, when the P value is less than 5%, we cannot reject the null hypothesis meaning that the model has heteroskedasticity.

According to the result obtained, the P value obtained (0.6200) is more than 5% which mean that the model has a homoskedasticity. The result are shown in the table (3)

Table.5. Heteroskedasticity Test Beusch-Pagan-Godfrey

Heteroskedasticity Test Beusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-Statistic	0.547212	Prob.F(3,27)	0,6543
Obs*R-squared	1.776810	Proc.chi-square(3)	0.6200

Source: Table developed by the author after data analysis

5. RESULT AND INTERPRETATION OF THE MODEL

OLS regression is a method for estimating the coefficients of a multivariate linear regression by minimizing the sum of the squares of the residuals. It provides BLUE (Best Linear Unbiased Estimators) estimators. The equation to regress is as follows:

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TOP + \beta_2 ODA + \beta_3 K + \mu_t$$

The model tested gives the following result by the ordinary least squares method:

$$GDP = 4.071117 - 0.418203 TOP + 0.383315 ODA + 0.585290 K$$

The results are shown in the table below:

Table.6. Multiple-regressions Result

LGDP			
Variable	(1)	(2)	(3)
LTOP	1.095*** (0.0240)	-0.439*** (0.0206)	-0.418*** (0.0150)
LK		0.637*** (0.000)	0.585*** (0.0000)
LODA			0.3833 (0.0099)
Constant	16.445*** (0.000)	10.542*** (0.0000)	4.0711*** (0.1060)
R square	0.163	0.914	0.9333
Observation	31	31	31

Source: Table developed by the author after data analysis

The estimation of the coefficients of this equation will be done by the method of the MCO (ordinary least squares) whose principle is the minimization of the sum of the squares of the residues. We will use the software "e-view" to make this regression. The manipulation of the data on this software will also give us for the equation:

- The standard deviations of the coefficients that will allow the calculation of certain variables (Such as Student's t-statistic) necessary for the interpretation of the results;

The coefficient of determination denoted by R^2 which is the proportion of the variation of the dependent variable explained by the independent variables.

The closer R^2 is to 1, the better the model. The interpretation of this coefficient remains very limited in the context of multiple regressions because it does not involve either the number of explanatory variables or the number of observations in the sample. This is the reason why we will use the adjusted or corrected R-square (R^2_{adj}) because it fills the gap of the simple coefficient.

- The student t statistic, calculated for a sample size $n < 30$, makes it possible to test the individual significance of the coefficients at a given level of significance and degree of freedom ($n-k$) with k = number of parameters to be estimated. The calculation being carried out, we proceed to the significance test itself. The first thing to do is to formulate the hypotheses. From this regression, we will start from the global interpretation to the particular one. We will shed some light on the coefficient of determination, the Fisher F statistic and the Durbin Watson statistic.

After using E-views to run the regression the results are shown in Table 1, the outcome shows that all the variables are significant. The variable trade openness (TOP) is significant at 5%, while the variables K and ODA are significant at 1%, it's also to know that C is significant at 10%. The result point that, trade openness (TOP) has a significant and negative impact on the GDP. The value obtained after OLS regression of the coefficient of determination is 0.933326.

We know that the more R^2 is not far from 1, the better the model. We know that if Fisher's F statistic is greater than 10, then the model is good overall. In this case, the Fisher test gives a statistical value of 125.9848 which is well above 10. We therefore conclude that the model as we estimated it is globally significant. In addition, exogenous variables (OPN, ODA and K) have an overall influence on GDP.

Based on the decision rule, only the capital and ODA coefficients are individually and statistically significant at different levels of significance. By contrast, the coefficients of trade openness are not individually and statistically significant. But by putting a special emphasis on the probabilities of the variables, it appears that the opening variable has an individually significant coefficient because the probability (0.0150) is significant at 5%.

Indeed, when TOP increase by 1%, it reduces the GDP by 0.418%.this is due to Mauritania by opening his trade to the world allows competition between foreign product and Mauritanian product. Mauritania as at an embryonic stage is not strong enough to compete with foreigner product, so it will see it profit reduce until close. This will showily an impact negatively in the economy of Mauritania.

Official development assistant has a positive and significant impact on the GDP; this is because ODA is a source of capital for investment in development project. Capital (K) also has a significant and positive impact on the GDP. Capital as known in cob Douglas function, contribute to economic growth.

The coefficient of ODA (0.383315) has a positive sign. This means that ODA has a positive influence on economic growth. So any increase in ODA of one unit leads to an increase in economic growth of 0.383315 points. All other things being equal this situation can be explained by the key role played by the ODA on the economy of Mauritania.

On the other hand, the opening coefficient is negative. This coefficient of -0.418203 reflects the negative relationship between trade openness and economic growth.

Table 7: VAR (Vector Autoregressive

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
VARIABLES	dlnGdp	dlnTop	dlnK	dlnODA
L.dlnGdp	0.309*	-0.229	0.155	0.437
	(0.181)	(0.259)	(0.711)	(0.398)
L.dlnTop	0.333**	0.163	0.204	-0.0982
	(0.139)	(0.198)	(0.544)	(0.305)
L.dlnK	-0.0382	0.0643	-0.275	-0.144

	(0.0569)	(0.0813)	(0.223)	(0.125)
L.dlnoda	-0.0466	0.0661	0.273	-0.0751
	(0.0864)	(0.124)	(0.339)	(0.190)
Constant	0.0439**	0.00446	0.0865	-0.00105
	(0.0216)	(0.0308)	(0.0847)	(0.0475)
Observations	29	29	29	29
Lagrange- <u>multiplier test</u>	0.53854			

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

After taking into account the autoregressive impact of dependent variable (GDP), the results from Vector Autoregressive Model (VAR) in a first column suggests that, trade openness has a significant impact on economic growth of Mauritania. The sign of the coefficient differs from the previous model (OLS) such that this time the impact is positive, which means when all other factors remain constant, then if trade openness in Mauritania increases by one percent then the economic growth increases by 0.333 percent. This abides with my first hypothesis that there is a positive effect of trade liberalization on economic growth of Mauritania. The Lagrange-multiplier test for autocolleration is higher than 10 percent level of p-value which means we fail to reject the null hypothesis that there is no autocorrelation in the model.

6. CONCLUSION

The link between trade liberalization and economic growth continues to fuel debate. The question that was asked in this study was whether trade liberalization has a positive or negative effect on Mauritania's economic growth. The response to this problem can have important implications for policy decisions on trade liberalization. The new theory of growth suggests that international trade allows the transfer and development of technology and consequently the growth of the economy will be stimulated.

With this in mind, international organizations have recommended that developing countries initiate liberalization policies. However, the latter must differ according to the stage of development of the country, because access policies on an immediate opening could prove to be inefficient if they are carried out at a premature stage of development of the country.

The impact of trade openness on economic growth is debated in the existing literature, the impact was positive in some studies and not significant or negative in others. The mixed results could be attributed to the country's analytical framework and specific characteristics. This study examines the impact of trade openness on Mauritania's economic growth over the period 1986-2016.

The OLS model and Vector Autoregressive model (VAR) was used in this study to estimate the regression. Economic growth which is measured by GDP was used as dependent variable and trade openness (OPN), gross domestic capital formation (K) and Official development assistant (ODA) as independent variables.

The results of the regression show that there is a positive relationship between Gross Domestic Capital formation (K) and Official Development Assistant (ODA) on economic growth. The result also shows that there is not a positive relationship between trade openness and economic growth in Mauritania, in fact the gains obtained from trade openness have not a significant effect to cover all the losses inherent in this process and this because of the economic structure of the country. There is a need to increase the effectiveness of the production tool in order to allow a better productivity of the factors.

Since the results obtained from the OLS regression are unreliable, we used the VAR model which is more reliable than OLS model to better reach our objective; the results obtained show a positive relationship between growth and Trade liberalization. This abides with my first hypothesis that there is a positive effect of trade openness on economic growth in Mauritania before embarking on over-ambitious liberalization policies, a developing country, Mauritania in particular, must first and foremost try to achieve relative stability, at the economic, political and social levels. Must be initiated, both by the Government and the international community, to improve its economic efficiency and achieve rapid growth

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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